

GDPR Compliance

Dear participant,

This survey seeks to understand people's perspectives on the desirable properties of data that people can get access to by exercising their GDPR rights. Under the GDPR Chapter 3 (Article 15), you have the right to request and download a copy of your personal data from various platforms, which includes the information they collect about you. To make the data comprehensible for end-users, GDPR also prescribes different desiderata of these data reporting. In this survey, you will be asked to evaluate the implementation of GDPR Article 15 by different platforms providing similar services.

This survey is being conducted jointly by academic researchers from XYZ. Your valuable opinion expressed in this survey may contribute to important research findings. So we request you to read the instructions meticulously, and answer all the questions judiciously.

Results from the survey may be published in a research forum. The insights will be published in aggregate forms (such as averages and/or totals). We will neither publish nor share any information which will disclose any of your confidential information. All information will be protected to the greatest extent allowed by law, and data will be kept secured during and after the survey.

Selecting the "Agree" button indicates the following:

1. You have read the above information.
2. You voluntarily agree to participate in the "GDPR Compliance" survey.

* Indicates required question

1. I consent; begin the survey. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

2. Please enter your Prolific ID here *

Background on GDPR Chapter 3: Rights of the Data Subjects

Under the GDPR Chapter 3 (Article 15), users have the right to request and download a copy of their personal data from various platforms, which includes the information they collect about you.

Let's take TikTok for an example. If you have been using TikTok short form video platform, you can go and request your data on the TikTok App and get a snippet of your data.

For the process of how to request your data and how a standard TikTok data looks like please refer to the information at this given url:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Q9mlrD20G3t7KQ8626ML1kAwxKFqyTVq?usp=sharing>

3. Before taking this survey, were you aware of having such rights to access your personal data gathered by different online platforms? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

4. If yes, how did you know about these rights? *

5. Have you ever requested your personal data from any platform? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

6. If you had made a request earlier, what was the reason behind it? *

7. Now that you are aware of the existence of such a right to your personal data, how likely are you to exercise this right? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very likely

Preferred format of content - **Browsing history**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the browsing history. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

8. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Title : Watched video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Watch Duration : 120 seconds Percentage Watched : 75</p> <p>Device : Mobile - Android Watched On Network : Wifi</p>	<p>Header : Platform B Title : Watched video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Products : [Platform B]</p> <p>Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : PlatformB watch history. You can control these settings here.</p>

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

9. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Title : Watched video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Watch Duration : 120 seconds Percentage Watched : 75</p> <p>Device : Mobile - Android Watched On Network : Wifi</p>	<p>Header : Platform B Title : Watched video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Products : [Platform B]</p> <p>Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : PlatformB watch history. You can control these settings here.</p>

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

10. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Title : Watched video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Watch Duration : 120 seconds Percentage Watched : 75</p> <p>Device : Mobile - Android Watched On Network : Wifi</p>	<p>Header : Platform B Title : Watched video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Products : [Platform B]</p> <p>Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : PlatformB watch history. You can control these settings here.</p>

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

11. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Title : Watched video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Watch Duration : 120 seconds Percentage Watched : 75</p> <p>Device : Mobile - Android Watched On Network : Wifi</p>	<p>Header : Platform B Title : Watched video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Products : [Platform B]</p> <p>Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : PlatformB watch history. You can control these settings here.</p>

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

Preferred format of content - Likes

In this section, we display how different platforms present the liked content. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

12. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Author : channel_name Video Url : 👍 Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET	Title : video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Reaction type : Heart Device : Mobile - Android

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

13. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Author : channel_name Video Url : 👍 Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET	Title : video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Reaction type : Heart Device : Mobile - Android

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

14. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Author : channel_name Video Url : Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET	Title : video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Reaction type : Heart Device : Mobile - Android

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

15. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Author : channel_name Video Url : Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET	Title : video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Reaction type : Heart Device : Mobile - Android

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Comments**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the comments. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

16. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Title : video title Author : channel name Comment : "Hi !! How are you" Comment ID : 12242n454 Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET	Comment : "Hi !! How are you" Media owner : Virat Kohli Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

17. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Title : video title Author : channel name Comment : "Hi !! How are you" Comment ID : 12242n454 Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET	Comment : "Hi !! How are you" Media owner : Virat Kohli Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

18. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Title : video title Author : channel name Comment : "Hi !! How are you" Comment ID : 12242n454 Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET	Comment : "Hi !! How are you" Media owner : Virat Kohli Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

19. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Title : video title Author : channel name Comment : "Hi !! How are you" Comment ID : 12242n454 Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET	Comment : "Hi !! How are you" Media owner : Virat Kohli Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Saved**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the saved contents. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

20. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Note : Platform A displays posts for different collections in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Saved on : https://platform.com/122143242	Title : video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Collection : collection name

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

21. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Note : Platform A displays posts for different collections in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Saved on : https://platform.com/122143242	Title : video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Collection : collection name

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

22. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Note : Platform A displays posts for different collections in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Saved on : https://platform.com/122143242	Title : video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Collection : collection name

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

23. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Note : Platform A displays posts for different collections in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Saved on : https://platform.com/122143242	Title : video title Author : channel name Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Collection : collection name

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Search history**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the Search history. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

24. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Search Query : How to build pc Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Device : Mobile-Android Search Results Clicked : Tutorial by GV Search Results Shown : Tutorial by NV Tutorial by BM, Tutorial by AM</p>	<p>Header : Platform Title : Searched for how to build pc Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Products : [Platform]</p> <p>Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : PlatformB search history. You can control these settings here.</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

25. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Search Query : How to build pc Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Device : Mobile-Android Search Results Clicked : Tutorial by GV Search Results Shown : Tutorial by NV Tutorial by BM, Tutorial by AM</p>	<p>Header : Platform Title : Searched for how to build pc Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Products : [Platform]</p> <p>Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : PlatformB search history. You can control these settings here.</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

26. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Search Query : How to build pc Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Device : Mobile-Android Search Results Clicked : Tutorial by GV Search Results Shown : Tutorial by NV Tutorial by BM, Tutorial by AM</p>	<p>Header : Platform Title : Searched for how to build pc Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Products : [Platform]</p> <p>Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : PlatformB search history. You can control these settings here.</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

27. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Search Query : How to build pc Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Device : Mobile-Android Search Results Clicked : Tutorial by GV Search Results Shown : Tutorial by NV Tutorial by BM, Tutorial by AM</p>	<p>Header : Platform Title : Searched for how to build pc Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET</p> <p>Products : [Platform]</p> <p>Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : PlatformB search history. You can control these settings here.</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Login History**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the login history. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

28. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Device/Browser : Mobile Device OS : Android Device model : Samsung S20 Device Identifier : dfjgoireljgr Location : Newyork, US IP : 00.00.00.00 Login Method : Username/Password	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Cookie name : *****1223 IP : 00.00.00.00 Language Code : en User Agent : Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/117.0.0.0 Safari/537.36

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

29. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Device/Browser : Mobile Device OS : Android Device model : Samsung S20 Device Identifier : dfjgoireljgr Location : Newyork, US IP : 00.00.00.00 Login Method : Username/Password	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Cookie name : *****1223 IP : 00.00.00.00 Language Code : en User Agent : Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/117.0.0.0 Safari/537.36

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

30. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Device/Browser : Mobile Device OS : Android Device model : Samsung S20 Device Identifier : dfjgoireljgr Location : Newyork, US IP : 00.00.00.00 Login Method : Username/Password	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Cookie name : *****1223 IP : 00.00.00.00 Language Code : en User Agent : Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/117.0.0.0 Safari/537.36

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

31. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Device/Browser : Mobile Device OS : Android Device model : Samsung S20 Device Identifier : dfjgoireljgr Location : Newyork, US IP : 00.00.00.00 Login Method : Username/Password	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Cookie name : *****1223 IP : 00.00.00.00 Language Code : en User Agent : Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/117.0.0.0 Safari/537.36

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Connections**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the connections of the user. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

32. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Note : Platform A presents different connections like following, followers in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Author name : Virat Kohli	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Connection type : Following Author name : Virat Kohli

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

33. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Note : Platform A presents different connections like following, followers in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Author name : Virat Kohli	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Connection type : Following Author name : Virat Kohli

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

34. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Note : Platform A presents different connections like following, followers in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Author name : Virat Kohli	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Connection type : Following Author name : Virat Kohli

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

35. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Note : Platform A presents different connections like following, followers in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Author name : Virat Kohli	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Connection type : Following Author name : Virat Kohli

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Devices**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the devices of the user. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

36. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Device Type : Mobile Device OS : Android 11.0 Device Model : Samsung S20 Device Identifier : dfjgoireljgr Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET IP : 00.00.00.00	Last Login : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET User Agent : platform 346.0.7.32.89 (iPhone15,4; iOS 17_5_1; en-IN; en-IN; scale=3.00; 1179x2556; 635436977) AppleWebKit/420+

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

37. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Device Type : Mobile Device OS : Android 11.0 Device Model : Samsung S20 Device Identifier : dfjgoireljgr Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET IP : 00.00.00.00	Last Login : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET User Agent : platform 346.0.7.32.89 (iPhone15,4; iOS 17_5_1; en-IN; en-IN; scale=3.00; 1179x2556; 635436977) AppleWebKit/420+

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

38. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Device Type : Mobile Device OS : Android 11.0 Device Model : Samsung S20 Device Identifier : dfjgoireljgr Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET IP : 00.00.00.00	Last Login : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET User Agent : platform 346.0.7.32.89 (iPhone15,4; iOS 17_5_1; en_IN; en-IN; scale=3.00; 1179x2556; 635436977) AppleWebKit/420+

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

39. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Device Type : Mobile Device OS : Android 11.0 Device Model : Samsung S20 Device Identifier : dfjgoireljgr Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET IP : 00.00.00.00	Last Login : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET User Agent : platform 346.0.7.32.89 (iPhone15,4; iOS 17_5_1; en_IN; en-IN; scale=3.00; 1179x2556; 635436977) AppleWebKit/420+

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Recent Location**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the last known location or recent location of the user. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

40. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Imprecise Latitude: 0 Imprecise Longitude: 0 Precise Latitude: 0 Precise Longitude 0	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Latitude : 0 Longitude : 0 Accuracy : 80 Source of Location : GPS

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

41. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Imprecise Latitude: 0 Imprecise Longitude: 0 Precise Latitude: 0 Precise Longitude 0	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Latitude : 0 Longitude : 0 Accuracy : 80 Source of Location : GPS

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

42. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Imprecise Latitude: 0 Imprecise Longitude: 0 Precise Latitude: 0 Precise Longitude 0	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Latitude : 0 Longitude : 0 Accuracy : 80 Source of Location : GPS

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

43. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Imprecise Latitude: 0 Imprecise Longitude: 0 Precise Latitude: 0 Precise Longitude 0	Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET Latitude : 0 Longitude : 0 Accuracy : 80 Source of Location : GPS

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Autofill Information**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the autofill information to the user. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

44. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Phone number : Country Code : +49 National : Area Code : Local : Local Prefix : Local Suffix : Address : Address line 1 : Address line 2 : Address line 3 : Address level 1 : Address level 2 : Address level 3 : Address level 4 : Country : Germany Postal code : Email : example@gmail.com Last Name : Doe First Name : John</p>	<p>Phone number : Address : Email : example@gmail.com Name : John Doe</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

45. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Phone number : Country Code : +49 National : Area Code : Local : Local Prefix : Local Suffix : Address : Address line 1 : Address line 2 : Address line 3 : Address level 1 : Address level 2 : Address level 3 : Address level 4 : Country : Germany Postal code : Email : example@gmail.com Last Name : Doe First Name : John</p>	<p>Phone number : Address : Email : example@gmail.com Name : John Doe</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

46. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Phone number : Country Code : +49 National : Area Code : Local : Local Prefix : Local Suffix : Address : Address line 1 : Address line 2 : Address line 3 : Address level 1 : Address level 2 : Address level 3 : Address level 4 : Country : Germany Postal code : Email : example@gmail.com Last Name : Doe First Name : John</p>	<p>Phone number : Address : Email : example@gmail.com Name : John Doe</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

47. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Phone number : Country Code : +49 National : Area Code : Local : Local Prefix : Local Suffix : Address : Address line 1 : Address line 2 : Address line 3 : Address level 1 : Address level 2 : Address level 3 : Address level 4 : Country : Germany Postal code : Email : example@gmail.com Last Name : Doe First Name : John</p>	<p>Phone number : Address : Email : example@gmail.com Name : John Doe</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

Preferred format of content - **User's Content**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the a single content created by the user. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

48. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Content Type : Post</p> <p>Content Title : My First Vlog Content Description : My first ever video Latitude : 0 Longitude : 0 Has camera metadata : 0</p>	

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

49. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Content Type : Post</p> <p>Content Title : My First Vlog Content Description : My first ever video Latitude : 0 Longitude : 0 Has camera metadata : 0</p>	

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

50. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Content Type : Post</p> <p>Content Title : My First Vlog Content Description : My first ever video Latitude : 0 Longitude : 0 Has camera metadata : 0</p>	

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

51. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Content Type : Post</p> <p>Content Title : My First Vlog Content Description : My first ever video Latitude : 0 Longitude : 0 Has camera metadata : 0</p>	

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Activity Summary**

In this section, we display how different platforms provide the activity summary to the user. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

52. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Videos Commented till now: 200 Videos Shared till now : 100 Videos watched till now : 300 Total searches : 10 Total Likes given : 30 Total Logins : 100 Creation Date : Oct 1, 2021 2:01AM CET Last Activity Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Total Videos Uploaded: 10 Total Followers: 10 Total Following : 20 Average time spent per day : 3 hours	Videos Commented till now : 20 Videos Shared till now : 10 Videos watched till end : 30

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

53. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Videos Commented till now: 200 Videos Shared till now : 100 Videos watched till now : 300 Total searches : 10 Total Likes given : 30 Total Logins : 100 Creation Date : Oct 1, 2021 2:01AM CET Last Activity Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Total Videos Uploaded: 10 Total Followers: 10 Total Following : 20 Average time spent per day : 3 hours	Videos Commented till now : 20 Videos Shared till now : 10 Videos watched till end : 30

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

54. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Platform A	Platform B
Videos Commented till now: 200 Videos Shared till now : 100 Videos watched till now : 300 Total searches : 10 Total Likes given : 30 Total Logins : 100 Creation Date : Oct 1, 2021 2:01AM CET Last Activity Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Total Videos Uploaded: 10 Total Followers: 10 Total Following : 20 Average time spent per day : 3 hours	Videos Commented till now : 20 Videos Shared till now : 10 Videos watched till end : 30

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

55. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Videos Commented till now: 200 Videos Shared till now : 100 Videos watched till now : 300 Total searches : 10 Total Likes given : 30 Total Logins : 100 Creation Date : Oct 1, 2021 2:01AM CET Last Activity Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET Total Videos Uploaded: 10 Total Followers: 10 Total Following : 20 Average time spent per day : 3 hours</p>	<p>Videos Commented till now : 20 Videos Shared till now : 10 Videos watched till end : 30</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

Preferred format of content - **Off Platform Activity**

In this section, we display how different platforms present the off platform activity of the user. You will then be asked to choose the platform which suits best for each property.

56. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **concise**? *

Note : Platform A displays events for different apps/different websites in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Activities received from lifestyles.com</p> <p>ID : 12345353463 Event : VIEW_CONTENT Timestamp : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET</p> <p>ID : 12334345353463 Event : Purchase Timestamp : Oct 14, 2024 1:56 AM CET</p>	<p>Website Link : www.example.com ActionType : OPEN_LINK Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET</p> <p>AppName : Amazon ActionType : Add_To_Cart ActionContext : Puma shoes Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:58 AM CET</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

57. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **transparent**? *

Note : Platform A displays events for different apps/different websites in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Activities received from lifestyles.com</p> <p>ID : 12345353463 Event : VIEW_CONTENT Timestamp : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET</p> <p>ID : 12334345353463 Event : Purchase Timestamp : Oct 14, 2024 1:56 AM CET</p>	<p>Website Link : www.example.com ActionType : OPEN_LINK Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET</p> <p>AppName : Amazon ActionType : Add_To_Cart ActionContext : Puma shoes Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:58 AM CET</p>

Mark only one oval.

Platform A

Platform B

58. Which platform's data representation do you find to be more **intelligible**? *

Note : Platform A displays events for different apps/different websites in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Activities received from lifestyles.com</p> <p>ID : 12345353463 Event : VIEW_CONTENT Timestamp : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET</p> <p>ID : 12334345353463 Event : Purchase Timestamp : Oct 14, 2024 1:56 AM CET</p>	<p>Website Link : www.example.com ActionType : OPEN_LINK Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET</p> <p>AppName : Amazon ActionType : Add_To_Cart ActionContext : Puma shoes Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:58 AM CET</p>

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

59. Which platform's data format do you find to be in **clear and plain language**? *

Note : Platform A displays events for different apps/different websites in different files.

Platform A	Platform B
<p>Activities received from lifestyles.com</p> <p>ID : 12345353463 Event : VIEW_CONTENT Timestamp : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET</p> <p>ID : 12334345353463 Event : Purchase Timestamp : Oct 14, 2024 1:56 AM CET</p>	<p>Website Link : www.example.com ActionType : OPEN_LINK Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET</p> <p>AppName : Amazon ActionType : Add_To_Cart ActionContext : Puma shoes Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:58 AM CET</p>

Mark only one oval.

- Platform A
- Platform B

About you

In this section, you will be asked a series of questions about yourself. None of these sensitive details will be shared in a way which will jeopardize your privacy.

60. You describe yourself as *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

61. Age (in years) *

Mark only one oval.

- 18-25
- 25-30
- 30-40
- 40+

62. Which of the platforms do you use? *

Check all that apply.

- Facebook
- Instagram
- Tiktok
- Youtube
- LinkedIn
- Snapchat
- Twitter

63. Occupation *

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